

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Disseminated intravascular coagulation phenotype induced by oxidized high-density lipoprotein associated with increased mortality in septic-shock patients.

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SUPPLEMENTAL TABLE LEGEND

Supplemental Table S1. Demographic characteristics and clinical data of UCI SSP and NSSP, and healthy volunteers.

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURE LEGEND

Supplemental Figure S1. Plasma level of aPPT and correlation with oxHDL and INDEX in SSP. Plasma level of aPPT (A). Statistical differences were assessed by student's t-test (Mann-Whitney) for SSP and NSSP. * $p < 0.05$. Correlation analyses between: aPPT with high-oxHDL (B, upper-left panel, $r = -0.52$;

$p = \text{NS}$), low-oxHDL (B, lower-left panel, $r = -0.8695$; $p = 0.0005$), high-INDEXTM (B, upper-right panel, $r = 0.5094$; $p = \text{NS}$) and low-INDEXTM (B, lower-right panel, $r = -0.1357$; $p = \text{NS}$).

SUPPLEMENTAL MOVIE LEGENDS

Supplemental Movie S1. Representative time lapse in control non-injected condition. Representative time lapse of Tg(fli1:eGFP)^{y1} 4 dpf larvae non-microinjected in the heart with 8 nL of saline buffer (NaCl 0,9%)

Supplemental Movie S2. Representative time lapse in saline-injected condition. Representative time lapse of Tg(fli1:eGFP)^{y1} 4 dpf larvae microinjected in the heart with 8 nL of saline buffer (NaCl 0,9%)

Supplemental Movie S3. Representative time lapse in oxHDL-injected condition. Representative time lapse of Tg(fli1:eGFP)^{y1} 4 dpf larvae microinjected in the heart with 8 nL of oxHDL (75 ng).

Supplemental Movie S4. Representative time lapse in HDL-injected condition. Representative time lapse of Tg(fli1:eGFP)^{y1} 4 dpf larvae microinjected in the heart with 8 nL of oxHDL (75 ng).

Supplemental Table S1

Supplemental Table S1.

Demographic characteristics and clinical data of UCI SSP and NSSP, and healthy volunteers

Variable	Healthy Volunteers (n=39)	UCI SSP (n=26)	UCI NSSP (n=16)
Mortality at 30 days, %	0	46,2	50
APACHE II, median (IQR)	ND	23.5 (20.5-25)	25 (23-27)
SOFA, median (IQR)	ND	12 (9-13)	10 (9-13)
Age (ys), median (IQR)	60 (42-70)	64 (53-76)	65 (55-73.5)
BMI, median (IQR)	24.8 (22.9-29.5)	26.1 (23.8-30.2)	27.4 (25.3-28.7)
Male sex, (% of male)	54	54	75
Time of sampling (h)*, median (IQR)	NA	55 (50-72)	61 (49-70)
CRP (mg/dl), median (IQR)	ND	30,4 (24.8-32.4)	25.4 (19.2-27.8)
Resuscitation Fluid (Liter),median (IQR)	NA	6.1 (5.4 -7.4)	6.0 (5.2-7.6)
Blood lactate level (mmol/L)median (IQR)	ND	9.1 (7.2-13.9)	8.7 (6.6-13.5)
Norepinephrine (ug/kg/min) median (IQR)	NA	0.31 (0.22-0.59)	0.24 (0.18-0.57)
Renal replacement therapy*(%)	0	28,2	25
Corticosteroids, %	NA	81	69
Mechanical ventilation, %	0	100	100

Definition of abbreviations:

BMI, body mass index; CRP, C-reactive protein; APACHE-II, Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II score; SOFA, Sepsis-related Organ Failure Assessment, IQR: interquartile range (expressed as percentile 25th, percentile 75th), ND: non-determined, NA_ non-applicable

* The sample for analysis was collected always prior to connection to a renal replacement therapy.

Supplemental Figure S1

Supplemental Figure S1. Plasma level of aPPT and correlation with oxHDL and INDEX in SSP. Plasma level of aPPT (**A**). Statistical differences were assessed by student's t-test (Mann-Whitney) for SSP and NSSP. * $p < 0.05$. Correlation analyses between: aPPT with high-oxHDL (**B**, upper-left panel, $r = -0.52$; $p = NS$), low-oxHDL (**B**, lower-left panel, $r = -0.8695$; $p = 0.0005$), high-INDEX (**B**, upper-right panel, $r = 0.5094$; $p = NS$) and low-INDEX (**B**, lower-right panel, $r = -0.1357$; $p = NS$).